

Original Research

Beyond the Ecological Balance: The Role of Environmental Metrics in the Relationship Among Institutions, Finance, and the Energy Transition in Latin America (2002–2021)

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Abstract

This study examines the relevance of selecting environmental metrics for evaluating the energy transition in Latin America. The study uses panel data from 16 countries spanning 2002–2021. Subsequently, a fixed-effects model with Driscoll–Kraay standard errors is applied to compare the indicators generally used to measure environmental pressure: the per capita Ecological Footprint (EFpc) and the per capita Ecological Deficit (EDpc). This research also incorporates other variables spanning the institutional, financial, and environmental spheres to obtain a more comprehensive perspective. The results indicate that the choice of environmental metric is not neutral. When using the EFpc, the coefficients are stable, clear, and consistent. The EDpc, conversely, yields less consistent estimates and is dependent on the model specification. With the EFpc, the role of finance is found to exert a significant negative effect on the share of renewable energy. This negative effect is attenuated within the interaction between finance and climate readiness as the latter variable increases. Readiness thus appears to act as a mechanism that enables the financial channel to become a key component in a country's energy matrix. However, the use of the EDpc reduces the model's goodness-of-fit, as it weakens the theoretical interpretation of the financial and institutional effects. Consequently, the study provides evidence that the EFpc serves as a superior indicator for monitoring environmental pressures relevant to the energy transition, given that it is dynamic and sensitive to consumption, unlike the EDpc, which provides a structural snapshot of ecological imbalance.

Keywords: Ecological Footprint; Ecological Deficit; Renewable Energy; Driscoll-Kraay; Latin America.

Introduction

The energy transition toward lower-carbon economies poses a significant challenge for Latin America. As of 2024, the region is characterized by a distinct diversification of its energy matrix, with renewable and non-renewable sources coexisting. Renewable sources alone account for 69% of the total energy matrix; the primary contributor among these is hydroelectric power, which holds a 45% share, followed by natural gas, wind, solar, and biogas [1]. Nevertheless, efforts to shift energy matrices entirely toward clean sources constitute a slow process. In the short term, a drastic imposition of such a ratio might prove unviable, as it would reduce the energy available to society and impose unacceptably high energy prices. This, in turn, could drive a renewed reliance on the extraction or importation of fossil fuels, potentially beyond the limits of safe

recoverability, while pressure on ecosystems continues to mount due to the expansion of urban centers and economic development [2,3]. Consequently, accurately measuring environmental pressure is necessary for every nation, as it enables realistic environmental assessments and supports the design of more effective policies to fulfill sustainability commitments [4,5].

The literature suggests utilizing metrics based on ecological demand; the most widely employed metrics in studies of this nature are the per capita Ecological Footprint (EFpc), defined as human demand on the planet's regenerative capacity, and the Ecological Deficit (EDpc), conceived as the difference between the environmental demand exerted by humans and their economies, and a country's biological regenerative capacity [5,6]. Both metrics provide insight into environmental performance, yet they differ in how they are interpreted from an economic perspective. The EFpc enables comparisons of consumption styles and development patterns across nations, whereas the EDpc reveals the magnitude of the accumulated imbalance [7,8].

In the context of the energy transition, the development of the financial system is of significant importance. The expansion of capital markets produces two entirely contradictory effects: One is that the expansion facilitates access to capital for initiatives relevant to environmental protection; the other is that it intensifies investment flows into traditional energy sectors due to resource demand [9,10]. The distinction in the use of financial channels stems from the prevailing governance type: countries with greater environmental readiness and robust regulations tend to accelerate financing for green or renewable projects [11,12,13]. According to international evidence, institutional quality enables both public and private capital to contribute effectively to the deployment of renewable energy. Notable examples include Costa Rica (which experiences cycles of 100% renewable electricity), Uruguay (with an Economy, Environment, Social, Government Index Score of 73), and Chile (which demonstrates average performance in the Climate Change Performance Index); these nations are rapidly scaling up renewable energy through the use of bonds and public funds, a trend that correlates with the highest regional environmental scores [14, 15].

Building on the foregoing, the present study takes a significant step forward by contrasting two indicators of environmental pressure, the per capita ecological footprint and the per capita ecological deficit, with the aim of determining which one most consistently and stably predicts changes in the share of renewable energies within the energy matrix of Latin American countries, thereby offering a metrological criterion for the formulation and evaluation of energy and climate policies.

This approach is grounded in the premise that EFpc serves as a measure of environmental pressure, as the indicator captures consumption patterns and energy-related behaviors [16,17]. EDpc, conversely, does not reflect such patterns; rather, it reveals the residual gap remaining when biological demand is weighed against biological supply. To test this hypothesis, fixed-effects models, specified by country and year, and featuring Driscoll–Kraay standard error estimates (lag = 2), are constructed using a balanced panel data set encompassing 16 countries in the region over the period spanning 2002 to 2021. This methodological framework not only deepens our understanding of the nexus between environmental sustainability and the energy transition but also calls for a conceptual re-evaluation of the use of ecological indicators in energy policy research. By comparing two indicators derived from the ecological accounting methodology established by the Global Footprint Network, the study demonstrates that the selection of an environmental metric is by no means a standardized process; indeed, the choice of metric fundamentally alters the manner in which we perceive the interconnections among finance, institutions, and environmental performance.

The remainder of this article is structured as follows: the study's methodology section is subdivided into theoretical foundations, a literature review, the methodological approach, and a description of the data used. The results, a discussion of the findings, and the concluding remarks are presented in the final section.

Theoretical Framework

The energy transition emerges as a multidimensional phenomenon characterized by the convergence of technological, financial, and institutional factors that, in concert, determine the pace and sustainability of the shift toward low-carbon energy systems [18,19,20]. First, the theory of institutional economics is typically situated within the classical institutionalism of the late 19th and early 20th centuries. Prominent among its

key figures is Thorstein Veblen, who, in his essay “Why is Economics not an Evolutionary Science?”, challenged the static nature of neoclassical economics. Also noteworthy is John R. Commons, who later gave greater shape to both the term and the analytical approach of this school of thought in Institutional Economics. Subsequently, Douglass North revisited and reformulated this tradition through the lens of New Institutional Economics, defining institutions as “humanly devised constraints” that organize and condition political, economic, and social interaction [21, 22, 23].

From this perspective, norms, both formal and informal, along with the quality of governance, reduce uncertainty and shape incentives, thereby enabling financial markets to channel resources toward green investments [24, 25, 26]. Consequently, the interplay between financial systems and institutions is crucial for understanding the energy transition: institutional capacity to absorb change determines the extent to which financial development can foster the integration of renewable energies [27, 28].

Secondly, the theory of green finance cannot be attributed to a single founder, as it emerged from the convergence of the sustainable development agenda and changes within the financial system. One of its most significant antecedents was the 1987 Brundtland Report, which cemented the concept of sustainable development as a central reference point in international discourse [29].

Subsequently, within the institutional sphere, this field began to take shape with the emergence of the United Nations Environment Programme Finance Initiative (UNEP FI) in 1991, formally established in 1992, with the aim of integrating sustainability criteria into the decision-making processes of banks, insurers, and investors [30]. Later, its operational consolidation was bolstered by the issuance of the World Bank’s first green bond in 2008 and the publication of the Green Bond Principles in 2014; these initiatives helped to establish transparency criteria and allocate resources to environmental projects [31].

That said, the theory of green finance is closely linked to the renewable energy transition, as it provides both the conceptual framework and the economic instruments needed to channel resources toward activities that facilitate the decarbonization of the energy system [32, 33]. In this regard, green finance emerges as a response to the limitations of the traditional financial system, which for a long time failed to account for environmental externalities, particularly those related to climate change and the intensive use of fossil fuels [34]. Consequently, this approach drives capital relocation toward projects in renewable energy, energy efficiency, energy storage, electrification, and sustainable infrastructure.

Furthermore, this perspective underscores the importance of factoring in climate, regulatory, and technological risks when valuing assets. This process causes investments in fossil fuels to gradually lose their appeal, while renewable alternatives become increasingly financially robust [35]. For this reason, the energy transition depends not only on technological advancements or political will, but also on the financial system's capacity to reduce the cost of capital, broaden access to sustainable investments, and establish clear criteria regarding eligibility, transparency, and sustainability criteria that enable the acceleration of the shift in the energy matrix [32]. Within this framework, green finance can be understood as a strategic mechanism that links environmental sustainability objectives with the investment decisions necessary to consolidate a low-carbon energy model.

Finally, the theory of ecological accounting, also known as environmental accounting, likewise lacks a single origin. However, its development can be understood through two complementary strands. The first relates to the growth of social and environmental accounting during the 1970s and 1980s, a period during which questions arose about whether traditional financial accounting was sufficient to capture the ecological impacts of economic activity [36, 37].

The second strand corresponds to its technical formalization at the international level, particularly following the 1993 publication by the United Nations of the Handbook of National Accounting: Integrated Environmental and Economic Accounting (SEEA), which is regarded as one of the foundational pillars of the system of environmental-economic accounting. In the same year, at the organizational and corporate level, a significant work in this consolidation process was Accounting for the Environment by Gray, Bebbington, and Walters. Subsequent studies have noted that environmental accounting has progressively acquired a more defined and autonomous profile [38,37].

Consequently, this theory bears a significant relationship to the renewable energy transition, as it proposes a method for measuring, recording, and valuing economic activity that extends beyond traditional financial

accounting. Its primary contribution lies in incorporating environmental costs, impacts, and benefits factors that are typically not fully reflected in conventional accounting systems [36]. Within the context of the energy transition, this approach enables a clearer identification of the ecological effects associated with both the use of fossil fuels and the integration of renewable sources.

To this end, it integrates variables such as carbon emissions, natural resource consumption, environmental degradation, energy efficiency, and ecological footprint into accounting information. In that case, ecological accounting serves as a valuable tool for supporting strategic decisions aimed at sustainability, providing more comprehensive evidence of organizations' environmental performance and enabling the evaluation of energy projects from a holistic perspective [39, 40]. Therefore, its contribution to the transition toward renewable energy lies in facilitating the inclusion of environmental costs in economic analysis, enhancing transparency in resource use, and strengthening accountability for progress toward a cleaner, more efficient energy matrix aligned with sustainable development goals.

In summary, institutional economics theory provides a crucial explanatory foundation for understanding the relationship between green finance and ecological accounting. It is premised on the idea that markets and organizations do not operate in isolation, but rather within an institutional framework that establishes incentives, constraints, and legitimacy criteria for decision-making. From this perspective, green finance can be viewed as a manifestation of institutional change aimed at redirecting capital flows toward activities consistent with environmental sustainability. Ecological accounting, for its part, functions as a technical and informational instrument that extends traditional economic logic by recognizing and valuing environmental costs and impacts.

Literature Review

The relationship among environmental pressure, financial development, and institutional effectiveness has been extensively studied within the energy transition framework. Nevertheless, the role played by environmental metrics themselves, particularly the manner in which various indicators capture sustainability dynamics, remains a relatively underexplored topic, especially in Latin America.

A primary line of research regarding the energy transition focuses on its institutional dimension, that is, the set of formal and informal rules, governance arrangements, state capacities, coordination mechanisms, and power relations that influence the speed, direction, and scope of energy change. This body of literature emerged, in part, as a response to the limitations of approaches that focused more narrowly on technological innovation and the diffusion of socio-technical niches. Although these perspectives have been key to explaining certain dynamics of change, various authors point out that they failed to accord sufficient importance to the ways in which institutions structure incentives, allocate resources, and entrench specific paths of energy development. In this regard, Lockwood et al., argue that historical institutionalism offers a particularly useful research agenda for analyzing sustainable energy transitions, as it facilitates an understanding of how path dependence, feedback effects, and power asymmetries either reinforce the persistence of fossil fuel regimes or, conversely, create space for change [41].

Within this line of inquiry, a central premise is that institutions do not merely constitute an external context for the transition, but rather an integral element that shapes its very outcomes. Public policies, regulatory frameworks, fiscal systems, ownership structures, and mechanisms for interest representation influence both the opportunities for renewable energy expansion and the resilience of traditional sectors. Aklin and Urpelainen, for instance, demonstrate that energy transitions must be understood as strategic processes shaped by political competition and path dependence [42]. From this perspective, external shocks do not, in and of themselves, generate change; rather, they interact with pre-existing institutions that may facilitate new trajectories, or, conversely, block them.

Another significant contribution of this literature is its emphasis on the multiscale nature of energy governance. The transition is not defined solely at the national level, but rather through the articulation among local, national, regional, and global scales. Kuzemko underscores that the politics of energy transitions are profoundly conditioned by global governance institutions that remain fragmented and, in many cases, have been oriented more toward energy security than toward decarbonization [43]. Consequently, the transition emerges as an uneven and asynchronous process, in which distinct rhythms, priorities, and

institutional capacities coexist.

Along similar lines, Newell argues that a global political economy of the energy transition must consider not only the role of states but also the influence of finance, multilateral institutions, and international power configurations [44]. From this perspective, national transition trajectories are conditioned by external constraints, geopolitical hierarchies, and unequal modes of integration into the global economy.

In Latin America, this aspect takes on particular significance, as institutional weakness, bureaucratic fragmentation, and a lack of continuity in public policy often hinder the effective achievement of energy targets [45, 46].

Another line of research analyzes the energy transition through the lens of sectoral governance and the political economy of energy policy. In the case of Brazil, for example, studies have shown that the expansion of renewable energy depends less on technical feasibility and more on how regulatory instruments, market incentives, and coordination between state agencies and business actors are designed and implemented. This approach proves particularly useful for Latin America as a whole, as it reveals that the transition is defined within a specific institutional architecture: regulatory agencies, government ministries, auction mechanisms, grid access rules, energy planning, and financing schemes [47]. In this sense, the institutional framework does not appear as a neutral backdrop, but rather as a contested terrain where decisions are made regarding the type of transition that can be undertaken, specifically, in whose favor, and at what social and territorial cost. Similarly, a significant portion of the recent literature challenges perspectives that reduce the energy transition to a mere problem of technological efficiency or the simple expansion of renewable energy sources. These studies argue that, in Latin America and the Caribbean, progress in the energy transition does not necessarily resolve structural issues such as inequality, territorial exclusion, or institutional weakness. On the contrary, when decisions are driven solely by a techno-economic logic, the transition may reproduce long-standing asymmetries and even exacerbate social and environmental conflicts. Consequently, several recent authors have begun to link the energy transition with the quality of institutions, social participation, multilevel coordination, and the capacity to articulate objectives of sustainability, equity, and inclusion [48,49].

Ultimately, this line of research converges on a fundamental idea: in Latin America, the energy transition cannot be separated from the construction of institutions capable of adequately planning, regulating, coordinating, and distributing the costs and benefits of energy change. Rather than representing a mere modernization of the sector, this process entails a political and institutional transformation that requires an active State, permanent mechanisms for implementation and evaluation, and multilevel governance capable of articulating the efforts of state actors, businesses, international organizations, academia, and civil society [50]. In this sense, the institutional literature offers a key insight into why countries endowed with abundant renewable resources do not advance at the same pace or follow the same transition patterns.

A second strand of analysis focuses on the role of financial development in environmental outcomes. This literature is premised on the idea that financial deepening, understood as credit expansion, capital market development, banking intermediation, or the increased sophistication of financial instruments, can significantly influence environmental quality. However, studies in this area do not yield a single definitive conclusion; rather, they suggest a somewhat ambivalent relationship. On one hand, a more developed financial system can facilitate investment in clean technologies, energy efficiency, and low-carbon infrastructure. On the other hand, it can also stimulate consumption, expand credit toward energy-intensive activities, and favor investment in polluting sectors, thereby increasing emissions and environmental degradation. This duality helps explain why the literature typically characterizes the relationship between financial development and environmental outcomes as contingent, nonlinear, and conditioned by institutional and structural factors [51].

Early seminal works in this field already cautioned that financial development does not operate in isolation, but rather interacts with economic growth and institutional quality. Along these lines, Tamazian and Rao found that financial and institutional development can help reduce environmental degradation by improving resource allocation and strengthening regulatory capacities [52]. Subsequently, Omri demonstrated a close relationship among financial development, economic growth, trade, and CO₂ emissions, highlighting that the financial system's environmental effects depend on its interactions with other macroeconomic dynamics [53].

In recent years, various studies have reinforced this idea by noting that the environmental impact of finance varies depending on the type of financial expansion that predominates. When this expansion is oriented toward innovation, efficiency, and technological restructuring, it can generate environmental improvements; conversely, when it focuses on expanding consumption and carbon-intensive production, its effects tend to be negative.

Based on this, a significant portion of recent literature argues that the relationship between financial development and the environment does not follow a linear trajectory. Some studies identify an inverted U-shape, or effects that vary depending on a country's levels of financial development, per capita income, and productive structures. Acheampong, for instance, demonstrates that the impact of financial deepening on carbon intensity varies across the stages of financial development of the economies in question [54]. Meanwhile, Khan distinguishes between direct and indirect effects, concluding that finance can influence emissions through economic growth and changes in consumption, investment, and the energy structure [55]. Along these same lines, more recent research emphasizes that simply measuring the size of the financial system is insufficient; it is also necessary to examine its composition, its sectoral orientation, and its capacity to channel resources toward environmentally sustainable activities.

In Latin America, this discussion takes on particular significance. The region features highly heterogeneous financial markets, substantial infrastructure investment needs, and an incomplete energy transition. Consequently, the literature has begun to devote greater attention not only to financial development in broad terms but also to the emergence of specific sustainable finance instruments. The most recent evidence for Latin America suggests that technological and financial development can serve as a catalyst for the energy transition, although its effects remain uneven across countries and depend largely on local public policy conditions and institutional capacity [56]. In a similar vein, Economic Commission for Latin America and the Caribbean (ECLAC), notes that, the growth of the sustainable bond market in Latin America and the Caribbean is positively correlated with the expansion of per capita renewable energy capacity, though it is not, on its own, sufficient to bring about a structural transformation of the energy matrix. In other words, regional literature indicates that financial development can contribute to improved environmental outcomes, but only when accompanied by regulatory frameworks, incentives, and coordination mechanisms that steer financing toward decarbonization activities [57]. Taken together, this second line of inquiry yields a central insight: financial development produces neither a singular nor an automatic effect on environmental outcomes. Its impact depends on the type of intermediation that predominates, the financial system's maturity, institutional quality, and the presence of policies that align finance with sustainability objectives. Consequently, rather than assuming that greater financial deepening inherently leads to environmental improvements, this literature proposes examining how, through which channels, and under what conditions finance can contribute, or fail to contribute to, an environmentally sustainable energy transition [58,59].

Finally, a third strand of the literature, albeit less developed, addresses the measurement of environmental pressure. Traditional indicators, such as CO₂ emissions or energy intensity, allow for observing specific dimensions of environmental degradation; however, they frequently prove insufficient to reflect the broader biophysical constraints associated with economic activity. In this context, indicators based on the concept of "footprints" have gained increasing relevance. The ecological footprint, for instance, measures the demand that human consumption places on ecosystems by integrating various dimensions of resource use into a single metric. Conversely, the ecological deficit expresses the gap between this ecological demand and the available biocapacity; thus, it accounts for accumulated imbalances rather than immediate or contemporaneous pressure [60].

Various recent studies point out that these indicators cannot be considered equivalent, as each captures distinct temporal and structural dimensions of sustainability. While the ecological footprint tends to respond more sensitively to short-term changes in consumption patterns and energy use, the ecological deficit is more heavily influenced by structural factors, such as land availability or historical resource use. This distinction is particularly important for public policy analysis, as selecting a specific metric can significantly alter both empirical results and their interpretation [61].

Furthermore, this body of literature underscores that expanded indicators offer a significant analytical advantage over traditional metrics, as they enable observation of environmental pressure from a

multidimensional perspective rather than solely through the lens of a single externality. In this regard, the concept of a "family of environmental footprints" has gained momentum in recent years, precisely because it brings together various dimensions (such as carbon, energy, land, water, materials, nitrogen, and phosphorus, among others) and facilitates a broader understanding of the balances and tensions between economic growth, resource consumption, and sustainability. Similarly, research inspired by the planetary boundaries framework argues that sustainability assessments must account for absolute thresholds, rather than limit themselves solely to relative improvements in efficiency. This is because an economy may become less carbon or energy-intensive while still increasing its overall pressure on ecosystems [62,63].

Despite these advances, empirical studies that directly compare different environmental metrics within a single econometric framework remain scarce, particularly in research focusing on the nexus between finance, institutions, and energy. This gap is even more pronounced in Latin America, a region characterized by significant heterogeneity in institutional capacity and environmental conditions. Addressing this void, the present study seeks to contribute to the literature by systematically comparing the ecological footprint and the ecological deficit as alternative indicators of environmental pressure. In doing so, it offers a more precise evaluation of how measurement choices can influence conclusions regarding the energy transition in emerging economies, as we can see in the next figure:

Fig.1: Research's Theoretical and Literature Background

Figure 1 shows that the relationship among financial development, institutions, and renewable energy is expected to operate through distinct yet interconnected mechanisms. Financial development increases the availability of credit, investment instruments, and market intermediation, thereby expanding the pool of capital available for allocation across sectors. However, this expansion is not inherently green. In the absence of enabling institutions, deeper financial systems may continue to favor incumbent sectors, short-term profitability, and carbon-intensive activities, particularly where fossil-fuel-based infrastructures remain economically dominant.

Institutions shape this allocation process by reducing uncertainty, strengthening policy credibility, and enhancing the coordination capacity needed for long-term energy investments. In this study, climate readiness and government effectiveness capture two complementary institutional channels. Readiness reflects the broader capacity to absorb and implement transition-related investment, including governance quality, social capacity, and economic preparedness. Government effectiveness, by contrast, refers to the administrative and regulatory capacity to design, implement, and sustain public action. Together, these institutional dimensions help determine whether financial depth is translated into renewable energy deployment or remains tied to conventional energy structures.

Environmental metrics enter this framework not merely as background controls, but as indicators of ecological pressures within which the institutional-financial relationship unfolds. EFpc is expected to proxy contemporaneous environmental pressure associated with current patterns of consumption, resource use, and energy demand. As such, it is more likely to align with short- to medium-term institutional and financial dynamics. By contrast, EDpc reflects the accumulated gap between ecological demand and available biocapacity. It therefore captures a more structural sustainability imbalance, one that may be linked to renewable energy outcomes through slower and more reactive adjustment processes.

From this perspective, the paper does not assume that all environmental indicators play the same analytical role. Rather, it argues that the observed relationship between finance, institutions, and renewable energy depends in part on whether ecological pressure is measured as a current demand burden or as an accumulated ecological overshoot. This is precisely why comparing EF_{pc} and ED_{pc} is analytically meaningful: each metric embodies a different temporal logic of environmental stress and may therefore reveal different transition mechanisms.

Conceptual Framework

We have incorporated the main variables of this study into this section to improve its understanding, viewed from different analytical perspectives and by various authors:

First of all, the ecological footprint per person serves as a basic metric for evaluating the environmental impact of human activities. The method calculates a population's ecological requirements by measuring the biologically productive land needed to support its resource use and waste management. According to the Global Footprint Network, the internationally accepted source, its calculation comes from the following mathematical formula:

$$EF_{pc} = \frac{\sum (P_i - Y_i) \times EQF_i}{\text{Population}} \quad (1)$$

Where P_i is the consumption of product i , Y_i = overall biological yield of product i , EQF_i = land type equivalence factor, and Population = total population. The sum encompasses all six land types: cropland, grazing land, forest, fishing grounds, built-up land, and carbon uptake land.

However, several scholars have developed their own concepts, such as William Rees and Mathis Wackernagel, who developed the ecological footprint model to measure human resource consumption relative to Earth's natural regenerative capacity and detect when human activities exceed environmental limits [64, 65].

The ecological footprint per capita represents the typical environmental requirements of one person, calculated in terms of energy use, food systems, and waste output, and is expressed in global hectares (gha) [66]. Scientists use specific categories of ecological footprint to analyze carbon, agricultural, and forest product footprints, enabling them to create targeted sustainability plans for different areas and social systems [67,68]). The measure serves as a crucial component of sustainability assessments because it shows the extent of ecological pressure that human populations impose. Research shows that rising per capita ecological footprints tend to correlate with better performance in national economic metrics, including GDP. The example shows that economic activities result in increased resource use and environmental damage as noted by Gao and Rajput [69, 70]. The growth of cities through urbanization increases ecological footprints per person because urban areas experience population growth and increased consumption, which deplete natural resources [71,72].

In a global perspective, countries exhibit wide variations in their per capita ecological footprints because of their economic systems, cultural traditions, and levels of technological progress. The high ecological footprint of developed nations persists due to their economies require large-scale resource extraction and utilization at elevated levels [73,74]. Emerging economies face increasing ecological demands, yet their consumption remains lower than that of developed nations because their economic expansion, along with shifting consumer patterns, reduces the gap between their consumption and that of developed nations [75].

The discussion about ecological footprint per capita persists because communities must find ways to connect economic growth with environmental protection. Assessing these components enables policymakers to develop sustainable systems that meet both social needs and economic requirements [76,77]. The implementation of adaptive practices for technological innovation development leads to a future in which ecological footprints decrease while biodiversity is protected for future generations [78,79,80].

In summary, the ecological footprint per capita serves as a basic indicator of environmental sustainability and resource use. The relationship between personal consumption patterns, economic activities, and

environmental regulations enables sustainable development by establishing equitable resource distribution and safeguarding natural systems for future generations [81,82]. Sustainability progress occurs through multiple approaches that address different elements of environmental and socioeconomic systems. The last concept, Biocapacity, is a critical measure of the Earth's capacity to regenerate biological resources and absorb waste, particularly carbon dioxide emissions from human activities. For the National Footprint and Biocapacity Accounts (GFN), the result comes from the following calculation:

$$EBC_{pc} = \frac{\sum_i (A_i \times YF_i \times EQF_i)}{\text{Population}} \quad (2)$$

Where A_i = available area of land type i , YF_i = national yield factor, EQF_i = equivalence factor, Population = total population

Also, it is defined as the amount of biologically productive land and water area necessary to provide the resources a population consumes and to assimilate the waste it generates, particularly organic matter and other residuals [83]. Therefore, biocapacity is a pivotal concept in sustainability, underscoring the balance between human demand and the Earth's ecological capacity.

The assessment of biocapacity considers various factors, including the yields of renewable resources, the technologies available for managing these yields, and the institutional frameworks that govern their utilization. It is typically expressed in global hectares (gha), providing a standard measurement for comparing ecological supply across regions and countries [84]. This measure includes land used for food production, timber harvests, and carbon dioxide absorption, encompassing multiple land types such as cropland, forest land, grazing land, and fishing grounds [85,86].

As populations continue to grow and consumption patterns become more resource-intensive, the concept of biocapacity has gained increased attention from researchers, policymakers, and environmentalists. The idea emphasizes that humanity's biocapacity is inherently limited, constrained by natural biophysical processes and the planet's ecological limits [87,88]. For example, in many parts of the world, biocapacity has been significantly depleted by unsustainable agricultural practices, deforestation, and overfishing, leading to ecological deficits in which human consumption exceeds the Earth's capacity to regenerate resources [89,90]. In addition, another international comparisons of biocapacity reveal stark disparities among nations. Wealthier nations often consume resources at a rate that their local biocapacity cannot sustain, leading them to rely on resource imports from less developed regions, which may possess surplus biocapacity [90,91]. Therefore, understanding biocapacity is essential not only for assessing national sustainability but also for considering global equity and environmental justice.

Biocapacity, therefore, acts as both a tool and a concept that underpins efforts toward sustainable resource management and environmental stewardship. It emphasizes the need for Earth's ecosystems' integrity while providing for human needs. As such, ongoing research into biocapacity and its interaction with ecological footprints remains vital to informing policies aimed at achieving sustainability goals and mitigating environmental degradation [92].

Table 1. Biocapacity's component

Component	Definition
Cropland	Bioproductive surface area dedicated to producing food and fiber for human consumption, fodder for livestock, oilseeds, and rubber; it is the type of land with the highest bioproductivity in the accounts.
Grazing land	Bioproductive areas used for grazing and forage production that support extensive livestock farming.
Forest land(products)	Forest area that provides timber, pulp, and other forest products; in the accounts, it is distinguished from its function of CO ₂ capture.
Forest land (CO ₂)	The portion of forest land required for the biological sequestration of CO ₂ (often referred

Component	Definition
capture)	to as “carbon uptake land”) associated with the carbon footprint within the framework of the Ecological Footprint.
Fishing grounds	Marine and inland water areas with available fishery biomass capable of sustaining the regenerative harvesting of fish and shellfish.
Built-up land	Bioproductive surface area occupied by infrastructure (housing, industry, transport) that has been converted from uses such as cropland or forest land.

Note: The definitions of the biocapacity components are based on the methodology of the National Footprint and Biocapacity Accounts developed by the Global Footprint Network [93]. The classification and use of yield and equivalence factors to express all flows in global hectares (gha) are documented in Borucke et al. and updated by Lin [94,95]. The distinction between cropland, rangeland, forests for products, forests for carbon sequestration, fishing grounds, and urbanized areas follows the original proposal by Wackernagel and Rees [96].

Then, the concept of an ecological deficit serves as a critical measure for understanding the relationship between human activities and their environmental impacts. An ecological deficit occurs when the population’s ecological footprint exceeds the environment’s biological capacity to regenerate the resources consumed and absorb the waste produced. This imbalance highlights unsustainable practices that can lead to long-term ecosystem degradation and the depletion of natural resources.

Ecological deficit is closely tied to the concept of ecological footprint, which quantifies the demand placed on Earth's ecosystems relative to the biological capacity the planet can sustainably provide.

$$EBC_{pc} - EF_{pc} = ED_{pc} \quad (3)$$

For instance, Sumaila emphasizes that just as financial deficits can have detrimental economic consequences, ecological deficits must also be addressed to avoid long-term environmental impacts [97]. This is supported by other researchers who illustrate how continuous ecological deficits lead to significant ecological degradation, which adversely affects both current and future generations [98,99].

Regions across the globe exhibit varying degrees of ecological deficits, often linked to specific socioeconomic activities. For example, studies in Alborz, Iran, revealed that unbalanced land use and industrial development have persisted since 1992, indicating an ongoing ecological deficit threatening local sustainability [100]. Similarly, analyses in Zhangjiakou City demonstrated that the area has been in ecological deficit, emphasizing the need for sustainable development strategies [101]. Such deficits are also prominent in resource-based cities, where ecological footprints surpass the ecological carrying capacities due to high resource consumption rates [102].

Further illustrating the global nature of ecological deficits, the G7 countries have experienced prolonged ecological deficits, raising concerns about their ecological sustainability without significant policy changes [98]. Findings across regions indicate that the management of natural resources, urban planning, and economic policies are interlinked, as sustainably managing these aspects is crucial to reversing the trend of ecological deficits [103,104].

The implications of an ecological deficit extend beyond mere environmental concerns; they also intersect with economic stability. Research indicates that in countries with an ecological deficit, natural resource rents tend to exacerbate environmental degradation, underscoring the complex relationship between economic prosperity and ecological health [103]. It underscores a paradox: economic growth achieved through resource exploitation can undermine the very foundations that sustain future growth and human well-being.

In conclusion, the definition of ecological deficit serves as an important yardstick for evaluating sustainability and resource management in both developed and developing contexts. The urgency of addressing ecological deficits cannot be overstated, as persistent deficits jeopardize ecological integrity, economic viability, and social cohesion across regions.

Therefore, based on the evidence presented, the following central hypothesis is proposed:

H1: The per capita ecological footprint is a more robust and coherent indicator than the ecological deficit for modeling the interaction between finance, institutions, and the expansion of renewable energy in Latin America.

Specific hypotheses :

H1a-Financial channel: Financial development alone does not drive the energy transition and may even slow it down in the absence of effective institutions.

H1b-Institutional moderation: Climate readiness positively moderates the financial effect on renewable energy participation.

H1c - Environmental metric: EFpc is hypothesized to have a negative association with renewable share because it reflects contemporaneous ecological pressure embedded in current production and consumption patterns. EDpc, in contrast, is hypothesized to display a positive association because it captures accumulated ecological overshoot relative to biocapacity, and thus may be associated with more reactive transition dynamics.

Materials and Methods

Study Design and Data Source

The study uses annual data from 16 Latin American countries spanning 2002 to 2021, totaling approximately 320 observations. The study measures the share of renewable energy as a percentage of total energy consumption, on a country-by-country and year-by-year basis. The key explanatory variables are: (i) Climate Readiness Index (read), (ii) Government Effectiveness (gov_eff), (iii) Financial Development (fin_index), and (iv) standardized environmental metrics, specifically, per capita ecological footprint (EFpc) and per capita ecological deficit (EDpc). Given that we have already elaborated on the definitions of the environmental metrics within the conceptual framework, we now provide an explanation of the remaining variables included in the model for the study at hand:

Government Effectiveness (gov_eff) is a sub-component of the Worldwide Governance Indicators, as measured by the World Bank. This indicator captures perceptions of the quality of public services, the civil service and its independence from political pressures, the quality of policy formulation and implementation, and the credibility of the government's commitment to these policies [105]. The Financial Development Index, developed by the IMF, allows us to examine two main pillars, integrated into a single robust index: Financial Institutions (FI) and Financial Markets (FM). Each of these pillars is further disaggregated into three dimensions: depth, access, and efficiency. In the case of Financial Institutions, "depth" encompasses indicators of size as well as banking and non-banking intermediation (e.g., credit extended to the private sector or assets held by investment funds and insurance companies); "access" serves as a proxy for the financial system's reach among households and businesses; and "efficiency" reflects the costs and performance of financial intermediation. In the case of Financial Markets, "depth" measures market size (e.g., market capitalization or outstanding debt); "access" reflects the breadth of participation and issuance activity; and "efficiency" is associated with liquidity and the capacity to allocate capital effectively [106]. Climate readiness, measured through the ND-GAIN Readiness sub-index (Read), assesses a country's capacity to mobilize and absorb investments, and to transform them into concrete transition actions. Its measurement encompasses three dimensions: (i) economic opportunity, related to the robustness of the economy and a business environment that facilitates the channeling of resources toward vulnerable sectors; (ii) governance, linked to political stability, security, and low levels of corruption factors that reduce investment risks, particularly for international investment; and (iii) social structures, which include human capital, the rule of law, and access to information and communication technologies, elements that enhance the viability of investment projects [107]. Furthermore, the econometric model incorporates interactions among the explanatory variables; given as noted in the literature, that investments in renewable energy are capital-intensive, require long-term horizons, and are exposed to regulatory risk, the effect of financial development (FD) on renewable energy adoption is not expected to be uniform. Rather, it is assumed that this effect depends on the institutional environment. Consequently, the interaction terms aim to capture the marginal effect of financial

development across two distinct institutional dimensions. The interaction with Climate Readiness (Fin × Read) is grounded in the premise that greater readiness capacity reduces investment frictions, uncertainty, and transaction costs, thereby increasing the likelihood that greater financial depth will translate into the effective deployment of renewable energy. Secondly, the interaction with Government Effectiveness (Fin × Gov) acknowledges that the energy transition relies on permitting processes, energy market regulation, tariff standards, grid planning, and the credibility of public commitments. The inclusion of both interactions allows us to distinguish whether the enabling environment that "greens" finance is driven primarily by absorptive capacity (Read) or by the effectiveness of regulations (Gov_eff), thereby avoiding the erroneous attribution of an effect to one dimension that actually belongs to the other.

In this context, the fact that an interaction is not significant does not invalidate its inclusion; on the contrary, it provides evidence of which institutional dimension effectively conditions the financial channel in Latin America. The table below presents a summary of the variables included in this study:

Table 2. Variable's sources

Variable	Type	Source
Renewable share (Ren)	Dependent variable	World Development Indicators (World Bank, 2024)
Climate readiness (Read)	Independent variable	World Governance Indicators (WGI) and Climate Policy Readiness Index
Government effectiveness (gov_eff)	Independent variable	World Governance Indicators (World Bank, 2024)
Financial development (fin_index)	Independent variable	IMF Financial Development Index Database (2023)
Ecological footprint per capita (efpc)	Key environmental metric	Global Footprint Network (GFN, 2024)
Ecological deficit per capita (edpc)	Key environmental metric	Global Footprint Network (GFN, 2024)
Interaction: Finance × Readiness (finXread)	Interaction term	Own calculation
Interaction: Finance × Governance (finXgov)	Interaction term	Own calculation
Country fixed effects (u)	Model component	Specification within FE estimator
Year fixed effects (γ)	Model component	Specification within FE estimator

Main Econometric Model

The following fixed-effects (within) model by country is estimated to capture intra-country variability over time:

$$\text{Ren}_{i,t} = \alpha_i + \beta_1 \text{Read}_{i,t} + \beta_2 \text{Gov_eff}_{i,t} + \beta_3 \text{Ecol_fp}_{i,t} + \beta_4 \text{Fin_index}_{i,t} + \beta_5 \text{interfin_read}_{i,t} + \beta_6 \text{interfin_gov}_{i,t} + \mu_i + \lambda_t + \varepsilon_{i,t} \quad (4)$$

Where $\text{Ren}_{i,t}$ denotes the share of renewable energy in total energy consumption in country i and year t ; $\text{Read}_{i,t}$ captures climate readiness; Gov_eff measures government effectiveness; $\text{Fin_index}_{i,t}$ represents financial development; and $\text{Ecol_fp}_{i,t}$ corresponds to the environmental metric, alternatively measured as EFpc or EDpc. The terms $\text{interfin_read}_{i,t}$ and $\text{interfin_gov}_{i,t}$ are interaction terms included to test whether the effect of financial development on renewable energy varies systematically across institutional settings. Their inclusion

reflects the theoretical expectation that financial deepening does not have a uniform effect across countries or over time, but instead depends on the extent to which institutions can absorb investment, reduce uncertainty, coordinate implementation, and sustain credible policy commitments.

More specifically, the interaction $\text{interfin_read}_{i,t}$ captures whether financial development becomes more supportive of renewable energy in contexts with higher institutional readiness, understood as stronger economic, governance, and social capacity to mobilize and implement transition-related investments. By contrast, $\text{interfin_gov}_{i,t}$ tests whether the effect of finance depends on the effectiveness of the public sector in regulating markets, implementing policy, and providing credible administrative support for long-term energy projects. Including both interaction terms in the same specification allows distinguishing between two conceptually distinct institutional channels: absorptive readiness and regulatory effectiveness. This also helps reduce omitted-institution bias in the interpretation of the financial coefficient and avoids attributing an effect to one institutional dimension that may actually correspond to the other.

In this specification, the coefficient $\text{Fin_index}_{i,t}$ should be interpreted as the marginal effect of financial development when the interacting institutional variables are at their mean values, since all variables are standardized as z-scores. The coefficients on the interaction terms indicate how the marginal effect of financial development changes when climate readiness or government effectiveness increase by one standard deviation. In this way, the model is designed not only to estimate direct associations, but also to test whether institutions shape the direction and magnitude of the financial channel in the energy transition. An alternative version is also estimated, where EFpc is replaced by EDpc to compare the performance of the environmental metric.

All variables are standardized to facilitate the interpretation of the coefficients and interactions. Standardization is particularly important in an interaction-based framework because all regressors are expressed as z-scores, the main effects can be interpreted at the sample mean of the interacting variables, while the interaction coefficients represent slope adjustments associated with a one-standard-deviation increase in the relevant institutional dimension. This scaling enhances comparability across variables and helps limit the mechanical inflation of multiplicative terms, while preserving the substantive interpretation of conditional effects. Thus, the variable construction is shown as follows:

$$Z_i = \frac{(x_i - \bar{x})}{\sigma} \quad (5)$$

Model Selection

The choice of fixed effects allows for controlling for time-invariant unobserved heterogeneity across countries (e.g., natural resource endowments, basic institutional structure) [108]. Including year effects captures common global effects. Given the panel dataset, comprising 16 countries over a 20-year period, the simultaneous presence of heteroskedasticity, temporal autocorrelation, and cross-sectional dependence among units is to be expected, for instance, due to international energy price shocks or financial crises that affect the region simultaneously. The use of Driscoll–Kraay standard errors addresses the risk of cross-country correlation within the Latin American region (e.g., regional energy policies, trade shocks) and ensures that standard errors are not biased. Finally, the comparison between environmental metrics (EFpc vs. EDpc) directly addresses the study's objective of evaluating which indicator is more informative for the energy transition.

Lag Selection

In the main model, the Driscoll–Kraay estimator was employed with a lag of 2, following Hoehle's methodological recommendation. He notes that for annual panels with a moderate time dimension ($T = 20$) and a small number of units ($N = 16$), short lags allow correction for low-order autocorrelation without overfitting the variance-covariance matrix. This preserves degrees of freedom, avoids artificially inflating standard errors, and maintains the estimator's stability [109].

From a theoretical standpoint, a two-year lag is also consistent with the literature on energy transitions and financial markets. Havrylenko illustrates the common practice of employing two-year lags to account for lagged effects in the analysis of renewable energy capacity, reflecting the operational time lag, typically

ranging from one to two years between the approval of investments and financial flows, and the actual installation of capacity [110]. The study uses data from 2000–2023 across 19 countries, and demonstrates that lagged increases in renewable capacity ($\beta=0.36$; $p<0.01$) drive improvements in energy security. Therefore, this lag structure strengthens temporal identification and helps mitigate simultaneity concerns, while the fixed-effects specification accounts for unobserved time-invariant heterogeneity.

Diagnostic and Robustness Tests

Additionally, as robustness checks, the study incorporates Pesaran's CD test to verify cross-sectional dependence among the residuals. Subsequently, a Hausman test is conducted to compare the fixed effects (FE) estimator with the random effects (RE) estimator and to confirm the appropriateness of using the FE model and a VIF test is conducted to assess potential multicollinearity among institutional and financial variables. Because VIF is a regressor-based diagnostic, it is generally computed from an auxiliary OLS regression rather than from the fixed-effects estimator itself. In our case, OLS was used solely to assess multicollinearity among the same explanatory variables included in the main panel specification; it was not used for substantive inference. The fixed-effects estimates remain the basis for interpretation, while the OLS-based VIF serves only as a diagnostic check.

Also, to verify the influence of the selected lag on the results, alternative versions of the model were estimated using different lag specifications (0–4).

In line with the primary hypothesis, which seeks to evaluate which environmental metric best captures the ecological pressure associated with the Latin American energy transition, the econometric model maintains an identical specification when estimating EFpc and EDpc. The incorporated interaction terms are guided strictly by institutional theory, which posits that the influence of financial development may depend on institutional quality rather than on the absolute level of environmental pressure. For this reason, an interaction term of the type "Finance \times Environmental Metric" is not included; doing so would imply testing a distinct hypothesis, namely, that the financial effect varies according to the degree of ecological stress, which would divert the analytical focus toward mechanisms peripheral to the study's core objective. The interaction structure is therefore grounded in theory rather than introduced in an exploratory manner. The aim is not to estimate every possible multiplicative combination, but to test a specific institutional hypothesis: whether financial development supports the expansion of renewable energy only under enabling institutional conditions. For this reason, the specification retains the two institutional interaction terms across all models and varies only the environmental metric, ensuring that differences between EFpc and EDpc are not confounded by changes in the model's conditioning structure.

A potential endogeneity issue in this study is the possibility of reverse causality between financial development and renewable energy deployment. While deeper financial systems may support the expansion of renewable energy, advances in renewable energy may also foster financial market development by generating new investment demand, expanding green financing instruments, and increasing overall capital-market activity. The empirical strategy helps mitigate, although not completely remove, this concern. Country fixed effects account for time-invariant differences across countries, year fixed effects capture common macroeconomic and regional shocks, and the two-year lag structure reduces simultaneity concerns by allowing financial conditions time to affect energy outcomes. In addition, Driscoll–Kraay standard errors address serial correlation, heteroskedasticity, and cross-sectional dependence. Therefore, the estimates should be interpreted as robust within-country associations that are consistent with the proposed institutional-financial mechanism, rather than as definitive causal effects.

Results and Discussions

Descriptive Statistics and Correlations

Table 3. Descriptive statistics of variables (2002–2021, 16 Latin American countries)

Variable	N	Mean	SD	Min	Max
Renewable share (Ren)	320	32.93	17.66	7.70	68.80
Climate readiness (Read)	320	0.00	1	-1.86	3.17
Government effectiveness (gov_eff)	320	0.00	1	-2.68	2.68
Financial development (fin_index)	320	0.00	1	-1.58	2.87
Ecological footprint per capita (efpc)	320	0.00	1	-1.41	2.96
Ecological deficit per capita (edpc)	320	0.00	1	-0.93	3.86

Table 3 summarizes the descriptive statistics for the variables used in the model. These descriptive statistics reveal clear heterogeneity among Latin American countries in their energy transitions and structural conditions. On average, the share of renewable energy stands at 32.93%, although the standard deviation is high (17.66 percentage points), indicating considerable dispersion across countries. Furthermore, the observed range, spanning 7.70% to 68.80%, confirms that the region comprises a mix of economies, with some strongly reliant on renewable energy and others heavily dependent on fossil fuels. Specifically, economies that are strongly reliant on hydropower, such as Paraguay and Costa Rica, exceed a 60% renewable energy, whereas those oriented toward hydrocarbons, such as Mexico and Venezuela, record levels below 10% [111,112].

Conversely, the institutional and financial variables, expressed as standardized values (z-scores), exhibit means close to zero and standard deviations of 1, as expected given the normalization process applied. Nevertheless, the observed ranges highlight significant differences among countries. The Climate Readiness Index ranges from 1.86 to 3.17, while Government Effectiveness varies from -2.68 to 2.68, reflecting considerable diversity in institutional capacity and public policy implementation within the region. Similarly, Financial Development ranges from -1.58 to 2.87, indicating varying levels of financial depth and access to capital markets.

With regard to environmental metrics, both the ecological footprint per capita (EFpc) and the ecological deficit per capita (EDpc) exhibit normalized means close to zero, though they differ in dispersion and value ranges. The per capita Ecological Footprint (EFpc) ranges from -1.41 to 2.96, while the per capita Ecological Deficit (EDpc) exhibits a broader range, spanning from -0.93 to 3.86. This suggests that the ecological deficit effectively captures more extreme variations linked to structural imbalances between ecological demand and available biocapacity. This difference aligns with the underlying logic of both indicators: whereas the Ecological Footprint reflects a more immediate or contemporary environmental pressure, the ecological deficit incorporates elements of accumulated and structural environmental pressures.

Taken together, these descriptive results validate the appropriateness of the empirical approach adopted, as they demonstrate sufficient variability in both the explanatory and dependent variable. This constitutes a crucial prerequisite for identifying robust econometric relationships within a regional context characterized by high heterogeneity.

Regarding the correlation matrix presented in Table 4, the results align with the study's theoretical framework.

Table 4. Correlation matrix

Variable	(Ren)	(Read)	(gov_eff)	(fin_index)	(efpc)	(edpc)
Renewable share (Ren)	1.0000	-0.2207*	-0.0899	-0.2377*	-0.3420*	0.0981
Climate readiness (Read)	-0.2207*	1.0000	0.6578*	0.6387*	0.5331*	-0.2254*

Variable	(Ren)	(Read)	(gov_eff)	(fin_index)	(efpc)	(edpc)
Government effectiveness (gov_eff)	-0.0899	0.6578*	1.0000	0.5188*	0.2617*	0.0189
Financial development (fin_index)	-0.2377*	0.6387*	0.5188*	1.0000	0.4729*	-0.0272
Ecological footprint per capita (efpc)	-0.3420*	0.5331*	0.2617*	0.4729*	1.0000	0.0991
Ecological deficit per capita (edpc)	0.0981	-0.2254*	0.0189	-0.0272	0.0991	1.0000

Note: Values are Pearson correlation coefficients; * $p < 0.10$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$. All variables are standardized (z-scores).

First, the share of renewable energy shows a negative statistically significant correlation with per capita ecological footprint ($r = -0.342$, $p < 0.01$). This suggests that when contemporary environmental pressures are higher, the proportion of renewable energy in the energy matrix tends to be lower. Similarly, a significant negative relationship is also observed between the share of renewable energy and financial development ($r = -0.238$, $p < 0.01$), as well as with the climate readiness index ($r = -0.221$, $p < 0.01$). In sum, these results indicate that in the absence of sufficiently robust institutional conditions, higher levels of economic and financial development may be associated with more resource-intensive energy patterns. Conversely, the relationship between the share of renewable energy and government effectiveness is not statistically significant.

Regarding the explanatory variables, positive significant correlations are observed among the institutional and financial indicators. Particularly noteworthy are the relationships between climate readiness and government effectiveness ($r = 0.658$, $p < 0.01$), and between readiness and financial development ($r = 0.639$, $p < 0.01$). This suggests that, within the region, institutional and economic structures are closely intertwined. Furthermore, the ecological footprint shows significant positive correlations with the institutional and financial variables, indicating that higher levels of development and institutional capacity may also be associated with greater environmental pressure from consumption. In contrast, the per capita ecological deficit shows no statistically significant correlation with most variables, including the share of renewable energy. This result reinforces the idea that this indicator captures more structural dimensions of sustainability that are less sensitive to the contemporary dynamics of the energy system. To summarize, these preliminary results suggest that the ecological footprint is a more sensitive and empirically consistent measure of short-term environmental pressure, whereas the ecological deficit appears to have lower explanatory power in this context. This initial evidence supports the appropriateness of comparing both metrics in the subsequent econometric analysis.

To avoid arbitrary empirical choices, the selection of a lag of 2 was tested using the Wooldridge test, which detected first-order autocorrelation in the residuals, and through sensitivity tests (lags of 1 and 3), with results consistent in sign and significance. Thus, a lag of 2 offers an optimal balance between statistical correction and temporal plausibility, ensuring robust estimates without excessive efficiency loss.

Table 5. First-Order Autocorrelation Test (Wooldridge; First-Differences Method)

Dependent Variable	Coefficient	SD	t	p-value	95 % IC inferior	95 % IC superior	F(1, 287)	Prob > F
Waste backlog (e_{t-1})	-0.1612	0.0594	-2.71	0.007	-0.2781	-0.0443	7.36	0.0071

Wooldridge's test for first-order autocorrelation, implemented in first differences, rejects the null hypothesis ($F(1,287)=7.36$; $p=0.007$). This indicates that the model's idiosyncratic errors exhibit first-order temporal dependence (AR(1)), meaning that past shocks affect current values. Consequently, we estimate a Fixed

Effects (FE) model with Driscoll–Kraay robust standard errors (max. lag = 2) to correct for heteroskedasticity, as well as temporal and cross-sectional dependence; the results are presented below.

Main Model: Fixed Effects with Driscoll–Kraay Errors: Ecological Footprint

Table 6. Main Results with Ecological Footprint

Variable	Coefficient	p-value
Climate readiness (Read)	-1.85	p = 0.02
Government effectiveness (gov_eff)	+0.52	p = 0.087
Ecological footprint per capita (efpc)	-3.86	p = 0.001
Financial development (fin_index)	-1.80	p = 0.021
Interaction Finance × Readiness (finXread)	+1.30	p = 0.057
Interaction Finance × Governance (finXgov)	-0.42	p = 0.279 (n. s)

Note: * p < 0.10, ** p < 0.05, *** p < 0.01.
n.s. No significance

Table 6 presents the results of the baseline model, estimated using country and year fixed effects with Driscoll–Kraay errors (lag = 2). In the specification employing the ecological footprint (EFpc), the model yields a within R² of 0.44, indicating that it explains 44% of the within-country variation in renewable energy share. The results confirm that financial development, on its own, has a negative and significant effect ($\beta = -1.80$, p = 0.021), suggesting that the expansion of capital markets does not guarantee increased investment in renewables in the absence of robust institutional environments, and a similar mechanism regarding readiness, requires other preconditions to be capable of acting as a driving force in its own right ($\beta = -1.85$, p = 0.02). However, the Fin × Readiness interaction term is positive ($\beta = 1.30$, p = 0.057), supporting the hypothesis of institutional moderation: the absorptive capacity for executing green projects conditions the financial sector's impact on the energy transition. Government effectiveness demonstrates a marginally positive effect ($\beta = 0.52$, p = 0.087), indicating that its role as a precursor to policies and regulations is significant in shifting the energy matrix; however, it is not self-sufficient.

The coefficient for the ecological footprint ($\beta = -3.86$, p = 0.001) confirms that as environmental pressure increases, the share of renewable energy decreases. This implies that, despite evidence on the state of their ecosystems, countries are not reversing the negative impacts on them; their economic activity remains anchored in traditional energy sectors that are intensive in fossil fuels and their derivatives. In summary, the ecological footprint coefficient serves as a proxy for contemporary environmental pressure; its sign and statistical significance remain consistent with the institutional-financial framework.

Alternative Model: Substitution using Ecological Deficit

Table 7. Main Results with Ecological Deficit

Variable	Coefficient	p-value
Climate readiness (Read)	-1.13	p=0.103(n.s.)
Government effectiveness (gov_eff)	-0.10	p=0.662(n.s.)
Ecological deficit per capita (edpc)	+9.88	p = 0.001
Financial development (fin_index)	0.46	p=0.738 (n.s.)
Interaction Finance × Readiness (finXread)	-0.22	p=0.726 (n.s.)
Interaction Finance × Governance (finXgov)	-0.10	p=0.761 (n.s.)

Note: * p < 0.10, ** p < 0.05, *** p < 0.01.

n.s. No significance

On the other hand, Table 7 reports the alternative specification in which EFpc is replaced by the ecological deficit (EDpc). Although the model retains a broadly comparable fit (within $R^2 = 0.42$), its internal dynamics change markedly. The ecological deficit carries a positive and statistically significant coefficient ($\beta = +9.88$), ($p = 0.001$), suggesting that countries with greater accumulated ecological imbalance tend to exhibit a higher share of renewable energy. This pattern may reflect a more reactive form of adjustment, in which renewable energy expansion takes place once ecological stress has already become structurally pronounced.

At the same time, under the EDpc specification, the institutional and financial variables, including both interaction terms, lose statistical significance. This suggests that although EDpc is positively associated with the renewable energy share, it does not preserve the institutional-financial mechanism identified in the EFpc model. In this sense, the ecological deficit appears to capture a broader and more structural dimension of sustainability, whereas the ecological footprint remains more closely aligned with the contemporaneous pressures through which finance and institutions shape the energy transition.

Visually, these results are reflected in the following figure:

Fig.2: EFpc vs EDpc Magnitude and Sign

Figure 2 reveals substantive differences in both magnitude and sign: EFpc shows a negative, statistically significant coefficient, indicating that the greater the ecological pressure associated with natural resource consumption, the lower the proportion of renewable energy in the energy matrix. This result aligns with the hypothesis that Latin American countries with higher biophysical demands tend to rely more heavily on fossil fuel sources, reflecting resource-intensive productive structures.

In contrast, EDpc has a positive, statistically significant coefficient. This suggests that it captures a different dimension of the transition process. Rather than reflecting contemporaneous environmental pressure, EDpc appears to proxy a more accumulated and structural form of ecological imbalance. Its positive sign may therefore point to a more reactive pattern, in which countries facing greater long-term ecological stress also tend to exhibit higher shares of renewable energy. However, because the institutional and financial variables lose statistical significance under this specification, EDpc does not preserve the same explanatory structure observed in the EFpc model.

Both metrics generate different empirical results because they do not capture the same dimension of environmental stress. EFpc reflects contemporaneous ecological pressures associated with current patterns of consumption, resource use, and energy demand, making it more responsive to the institutional and financial conditions that shape renewable energy deployment over time. On the other hand, EDpc measures the gap between ecological demand and biocapacity and therefore captures a more structural and accumulated form of ecological imbalance. As a result, it is less sensitive to short-term changes in policy or finance and more

likely to produce a different empirical pattern.

The results indicate that financial depth fosters renewable energy penetration solely within contexts characterized by high levels of institutional preparedness, consistent with the moderation hypothesis. However, the marginal significance of this interaction, along with the attenuation of its effect when assessed using the Ecological Deficit metric, suggests that the observed impact is sensitive to both the specific environmental metric employed and the modality of the transition.

Model Robustness and Validity Tests

Table 8. Robustness to the Number of Lags in the Driscoll–Kraay Estimator (EFpc model)

Variables	Lag 0	Lag 1	Lag 2 (Main)	Lag 3	Lag 4
Climate readiness (Read)	-1.852***	-1.852**	-1.852**	-1.852**	-1.852**
	(0.559)	(0.662)	(0.731)	(0.760)	(0.759)
Government effectiveness (gov_eff)	0.519**	0.519*	0.519*	0.519*	0.519*
	(0.223)	(0.265)	(0.287)	(0.290)	(0.278)
Financial development (fin_index)	-1.801**	-1.801**	-1.801**	-1.801**	-1.801***
	(0.702)	(0.750)	(0.713)	(0.664)	(0.598)
Ecological footprint per capita (efpc)	-3.862***	-3.862***	-3.862***	-3.862***	-3.862***
	(0.770)	(0.911)	(0.937)	(0.929)	(0.913)
Interaction Finance × Readiness (finXread)	1.299**	1.299**	1.299*	1.299*	1.299*
	(0.496)	(0.591)	(0.642)	(0.667)	(0.664)
Interaction Finance × Governance (finXgov)	-0.417	-0.417	-0.417	-0.417	-0.417
	(0.277)	(0.342)	(0.374)	(0.388)	(0.390)

Notes: Standard errors (Driscoll–Kraay) in parentheses. All models include country and year fixed effects. $p < 0.10$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$.

The results presented demonstrate the consistency and robustness of the model estimated under a fixed effects specification for country and year, using Driscoll–Kraay standard errors to simultaneously correct for heteroscedasticity, autocorrelation, and cross-sectional dependence. The estimated coefficients maintain consistent signs and levels of statistical significance across the specifications, reinforcing the stability of the findings. In particular, the reported statistical significance, indicated by the conventional levels ($p < 0.10$, $p < 0.05$, $p < 0.01$), confirms the strength of the relationships among the model's key variables. This methodological approach ensures that inferences are not biased by typical panel-data problems, thereby strengthening the internal validity of the results and supporting the interpretation of the estimated effects within the study's framework.

Fig.3: Robustness of the financial coefficient to the number of lags in the Driscoll–Kraay estimator.

Taken together, the results confirm that the findings do not depend on the choice of temporal bandwidth, reinforcing the empirical reliability of the model based on the EFpc metric. The diagnostic tests confirm the empirical and statistical validity of the model:

Table 9. Diagnostic test results

Test	Statistic / χ^2 / F/Mean	Prob. > χ^2 / F
Overall significance (FE, conventional)	F(25, 279) = 8.81	0.000
Overall significance (FE + Driscoll–Kraay SE)	F(25, 19) = 26.60	0.000
Hausman test (FE vs RE)	$\chi^2(6) = 5.50$	0.4815
Pesaran CD (cross-sectional dependence)	$z = -2.918$	0.0035
Rho	$\rho = 0.9776$	
F test (15, 279)	733.25	F = 0.0000
VIF	2.01	

Note: All diagnostic tests support the use of a fixed-effects model with Driscoll–Kraay standard errors. This estimator is consistent in the presence of heteroskedasticity, serial correlation, and cross-sectional dependence, making it suitable for macro-panel data with moderate time dimensions (T=20) and small cross-sections (N=16).

The results presented in Table 9 provide consistent evidence of the econometric validity and robustness of the estimated model. First, the Hausman test indicates that there are no systematic differences between the fixed and random-effects estimators, suggesting that both are consistent. However, the F-test ($p < 0.001$) and the high coefficient of variation ($\rho \approx 0.98$) indicate significant unobserved heterogeneity across countries, justifying the use of the fixed-effects model as the primary specification, especially in a region as diverse as Latin America.

Second, Pesaran's cross-sectional dependency test confirms the presence of contemporaneous correlation between countries. This result is consistent with the reality of an interconnected region, where common shocks, such as changes in international energy prices, variations in global macroeconomic conditions, or shared climate commitments, can affect several economies simultaneously. In this sense, the finding supports the use of Driscoll–Kraay standard errors, as they allow for more robust inferences regarding this type of dependency. The variance inflation factors (VIF) were estimated using an auxiliary pooled OLS regression that included the same regressors and year dummies as the main specification. The results do not indicate

any serious multicollinearity, as all VIF values remain well below conventional thresholds. In the baseline model, the highest VIF is 3.16, and the mean VIF is 2.01.

Similarly, robustness analyses of lag variation show that the model's main coefficients, particularly those for the ecological footprint, financial development, and their interaction with institutional quality, retain their signs, magnitudes, and statistical significance. This stability suggests that the results do not depend on a specific choice in the temporal structure of the errors, thus strengthening the model's internal consistency. In sum, these findings are relevant to the study's objective, as they support conclusions regarding the roles of finance, institutions, and environmental metrics in the energy transition that are not distorted by econometric problems such as autocorrelation, heteroscedasticity, or cross-dependence. This reinforces the credibility of the empirical evidence and supports the interpretation that the choice of environmental metric, particularly the greater explanatory power of the ecological footprint compared to the ecological deficit, represents a robust result and rather than an effect driven by the model specification.

The results section concludes with the following table, which shows how the hypotheses align with the results obtained throughout this work:

Table 10. Hypothesis vs Results

Element	Evidence	Hypothesis	Decision
Interaction fin×readiness (positive, p=0.057)	EFpc	H1a – Financial Channel H1b – Institutional Moderation	Accepted
EFpc negative (p<0.01)	EFpc	H1c – Environmental Metric	Accepted
EDpc positive (p<0.01)	EDpc	H1c – Environmental Metric	Accepted
R ² within Difference (0.44 vs 0.42)	EFpc > EDpc	H1-Main	Accepted

Discussion

The results of this study suggest that the energy transition in Latin America does not depend on an automatic relationship among finance, institutions, and environmental pressures, but rather on the way these elements interact. In the main model, estimated with country- and year-fixed effects and Driscoll–Kraay standard errors, financial development exerts a negative, statistically significant effect on the share of renewable energy when environmental pressure is measured by ecological footprint per capita. This finding is consistent with a strand of the literature warning that financial deepening may worsen environmental outcomes when it expands credit, investment, and consumption toward carbon-intensive activities rather than cleaner energy systems [113]. It also makes a simple reverse-causality explanation less plausible, since a mechanism running from renewable energy expansion to financial deepening would be more likely to produce a uniformly positive association. Instead, the evidence points to a conditional relationship in which finance becomes more supportive of renewable energy only when climate readiness is stronger.

In this regard, Tamazian and Rao argue that financial liberalization may harm environmental quality when it is not accompanied by a robust institutional framework [52], while Acheampong finds that several forms of financial development tend to increase CO₂ emissions when resources are directed toward conventional economic uses [54]. From this perspective, the negative coefficient on financial development suggests that, in the absence of sufficient institutional capacity, the expansion of capital markets does not necessarily translate into greater investment in renewable energy. Rather, it may reinforce existing energy trajectories by favoring sectors linked to fossil-fuel-based energy systems or projects with faster and more certain returns. This interpretation is also consistent with recent assessments of Latin America and the Caribbean, which emphasize that the region has substantial renewable energy potential but continues to face difficulties in mobilizing clean finance sustainably and translating that potential into effective deployment [114].

At the same time, the positive interaction between financial development and readiness supports the institutional moderation hypothesis. Although the statistical significance is only marginal, the sign of the coefficient suggests that the effect of finance shifts when countries possess greater capacity to absorb,

coordinate, and implement green projects. This result aligns with the literature that emphasizes the roles of state capacity and regulatory quality in decarbonization processes. Singh, for example, argues that stronger state capacity is essential for designing and implementing policies that promote renewable energy, mobilize investment, and reduce uncertainty [45]. Likewise, Lopez highlights that regulatory design and institutional stability are decisive for expanding renewable energy in Latin America and the Caribbean. In substantive terms, the positive interaction implies that the marginal effect of financial development becomes less negative, and may even become supportive of renewable energy, as climate readiness improves [115]. This confirms that finance does not operate as an autonomous driver of the transition; rather, its effect is conditional on the broader institutional environment.

The marginally positive direct effect of government effectiveness reinforces this interpretation. The results suggest that government quality matters as a facilitating condition for the energy transition, even if it does not operate in isolation. By contrast, the lack of statistical significance in the Fin-Gov interaction does not weaken the case for its inclusion in the model. Instead, it suggests that, in the Latin American context examined here, absorptive and transition-oriented readiness may constitute a more relevant conditioning mechanism than government effectiveness alone. This is also consistent with the broader institutional literature: energy governance can foster the transition, but its effects depend on how it interacts with economic, financial, and technological factors. Put differently, it is not enough to refer to “better institutions” in general terms; what matters is their concrete capacity to steer investment, mitigate regulatory risk, and coordinate public and private actors.

These results point to a sequential mechanism linking finance, institutions, and environmental pressure. Financial development expands the volume of capital available in the economy, but institutions determine the direction and effectiveness of that allocation. Where climate readiness is weak, financial deepening is more likely to reinforce incumbent, short-term, and carbon-intensive energy structures, since uncertainty, coordination failures, and implementation constraints remain high. Where readiness is stronger, the same expansion of finance is better aligned with renewable energy deployment because institutional capacity reduces transaction costs, strengthens policy credibility, and facilitates the execution of transition-related projects. Within this framework, the environmental metric shapes how the relationship is observed empirically: EFpc captures the contemporaneous ecological pressure under which these institutional-financial allocation decisions occur, whereas EDpc reflects a more cumulative ecological imbalance that is less directly linked to current policy and investment dynamics.

Another important finding of the main model is the negative and highly significant coefficient on the ecological footprint. This indicates that as contemporaneous biophysical pressure increases, the share of renewable energy declines. This pattern can be interpreted as evidence that countries placing greater demands on resources and ecosystems continue to operate under fossil-fuel-intensive production and energy structures, rather than alleviating that pressure through a more rapid transition toward cleaner sources [116]. This result receives indirect support from studies on Latin America that use the ecological footprint as an indicator of environmental degradation and show that regional ecological pressure is closely associated with natural-resource dependence, production structures, and domestic credit dynamics. In addition, the methodological literature on the ecological footprint underscores its usefulness in capturing, more comprehensively than CO₂ emissions alone, the human pressure exerted on natural resources and ecosystems [117,118].

The contrast with the alternative model is particularly revealing. When the ecological footprint is replaced by the ecological deficit, the environmental coefficient remains positive and statistically significant, but the institutional-financial channel loses significance. This suggests that EDpc may capture a more structural and cumulative dimension of sustainability, one that is less informative about the contemporaneous institutional and financial mechanisms associated with renewable energy deployment. In this sense, the finding may indicate that countries with larger ecological deficits respond more reactively to already entrenched ecological imbalances, increasing the share of renewable energy only once accumulated environmental deterioration becomes more visible or politically salient.

This points to an important analytical distinction between environmental metrics. The ecological footprint appears to capture more effectively the current ecological pressure that conditions the effectiveness of energy policies, whereas the ecological deficit more closely resembles a structural constraint on long-term

sustainability. The literature on environmental measurement supports this distinction: the ecological footprint was designed as an indicator of human demand on the regenerative capacity of ecosystems, while the ecological deficit expresses the extent to which that demand exceeds available biocapacity. As a result, the two indicators should not be expected to respond in the same way to annual changes in regulation, technology, or the composition of the energy matrix.

In substantive terms, the comparison between the two models suggests that the energy transition in the region may follow at least two distinct logics. When the ecological footprint is used, the evidence points to a more contemporaneous institutional-financial dynamic, in which current environmental pressures interact with finance and institutions to facilitate or hinder the expansion of renewable energy. By contrast, when the ecological deficit is used, a more reactive logic emerges, in which renewable energy expansion appears associated with accumulated ecological imbalances rather than with current institutional-financial capacity. Although this distinction should be interpreted with caution, it is consistent with the literature, which emphasizes that broader environmental indicators are not interchangeable but rather capture different temporalities of ecological deterioration [119].

The results also resonate with recent studies on the relationship between finance and renewable energy, which show that the effects of financial deepening are not homogeneous and instead depend on institutional, regulatory, and structural thresholds. Evidence from emerging economies indicates that financial expansion can stimulate investment in renewable energy under certain conditions, but not universally [120]. Accordingly, the finding that the interaction between finance and institutions is positive, even if sensitive to the environmental metric employed, is consistent with a growing body of research that characterizes the relationship between finance and the energy transition as contingent and context-dependent.

Finally, the robustness checks strengthen the credibility of this interpretation. The use of Driscoll–Kraay standard errors is appropriate in settings characterized by heteroskedasticity, autocorrelation, and cross-sectional dependence, particularly in regional panel datasets where countries are exposed to common shocks. In Latin America, such cross-sectional dependence is substantively plausible given the region's simultaneous exposure to international energy prices, global financial conditions, and shared climate-related frameworks [121]. In addition, the low variance inflation factors obtained in auxiliary diagnostic regressions suggest that multicollinearity is not a serious concern, including for the interaction terms. Because the main coefficients retain their signs and general stability across alternative lag specifications, the stronger explanatory power of the ecological footprint relative to the ecological deficit appears to reflect substantive differences between the indicators rather than a particular econometric specification.

Conclusion

This study provides novel evidence on the importance of environmental metrics for analyzing the energy-climate transition in Latin America. Using a balanced panel of 16 countries over the period 2000–2021 and a model with country and year fixed effects estimated with Driscoll–Kraay standard errors, the results show that the ecological footprint per capita (EFpc) constitutes a more robust, sensitive, and conceptually coherent measure than the ecological deficit per capita (EDpc) for capturing the type of environmental pressure most relevant to energy-transition processes.

One of the study's central findings is that the choice of environmental metric materially alters the interpretation of the results. When environmental pressure is measured through the ecological footprint, the estimated coefficients are consistent with the proposed institutional-financial framework. Under this specification, financial development exerts a negative and statistically significant effect on the share of renewable energy ($\beta = -1.80$, $p = 0.021$), while the interaction between financial development and readiness is positive and marginally significant ($\beta = 1.30$, $p = 0.057$). All these findings suggest that financial deepening does not automatically promote the energy transition and may even be associated with a lower share of renewable energy when adequate institutional conditions are absent. At the same time, the positive interaction indicates that this adverse effect weakens as institutional readiness improves, confirming that institutions act as a key moderating factor in shaping the effectiveness of finance within the energy transition. The ecological footprint also exhibits superior econometric performance, with a stronger within-model fit (R^2 within = 0.44) and yields an interpretation that is more closely aligned with the substantive mechanisms

underlying contemporary environmental pressure. In particular, EFpc appears to capture more effectively the pressure arising from resource consumption and the intensive use of the biophysical base, that is, a current form of environmental pressure that constrains countries' capacity to advance in the energy transition.

By contrast, when the ecological footprint is replaced by the ecological deficit, model fit declines (R^2 within = 0.42), and the empirical pattern changes substantially. The environmental coefficient becomes positive and statistically significant ($\beta = 9.88$, $p < 0.001$), while the institutional and financial interactions lose explanatory coherence. This suggests that the ecological deficit does not capture with the same precision the contemporaneous environmental pressures shaping the transition; rather, it reflects an accumulated, structural imbalance between ecological demand and biocapacity. Accordingly, EDpc appears to be less suitable for identifying the institutional-financial dynamics associated with renewable energy deployment in the region.

The robustness checks reinforce this interpretation. The stability of the main coefficients under alternative Driscoll-Kraay lag structures (lags 0–4) indicates that the results do not depend on a particular temporal specification. In addition, the low variance inflation factors obtained from auxiliary diagnostic regressions suggest that multicollinearity is not a serious concern. Ultimately, these results strengthen confidence in the model's internal consistency and support the central conclusion that the ecological footprint is a more appropriate metric than the ecological deficit for analyzing the environmental pressures most relevant to the Latin American energy transition.

An important limitation of the study is that, although the empirical strategy helps mitigate simultaneity concerns, it does not fully eliminate endogeneity. Reverse causality between financial development and renewable energy, together with omitted time-varying factors, may still affect the estimates. The findings should therefore be interpreted as robust structural associations rather than as strict causal effects. Future research could address this limitation more directly through instrumental-variable strategies, dynamic panel estimators, or quasi-experimental regulatory shocks. It would also be valuable to assess whether the analytical superiority of the ecological footprint holds across other geographical settings and historical periods, and to examine more closely which specific institutional and financial dimensions condition the effectiveness of finance in promoting renewable energy expansion. In sum, the findings confirm that institutions enable finance to support the energy transition and that the choice of environmental metric decisively shapes the conclusions drawn from the analysis. The ecological footprint emerges as the most suitable indicator for monitoring environmental pressures relevant to the transition given its dynamic nature and sensitivity to consumption and resource use. The ecological deficit, by contrast, offers a more structural perspective on accumulated ecological imbalances. The study, therefore, highlights the importance of selecting appropriate environmental metrics to understand sustainability transitions in emerging economies.

Contributions

This paper also makes contributions to the literature on the energy transition, environmental measurement, and green finance in emerging economies.

First, a methodological contribution by demonstrating that the choice of environmental indicator is not neutral in empirical analyses of the energy transition. By comparing the ecological footprint per capita (EFpc) and the ecological deficit per capita (EDpc) within a common econometric framework, the study shows that different environmental metrics can yield substantively different interpretations of the relationship among finance, institutions, and renewable energy.

Second, contributes to the literature on finance and renewable energy by showing that the financial channel is conditional rather than automatic. Financial development does not emerge as a uniformly supportive force for renewable energy expansion; rather, its effect depends on the broader institutional context, particularly the degree of climate readiness. This refines current debates by showing that deeper financial systems may either support green transformation or reinforce conventional energy structures, depending on the institutional capacity available to direct, absorb, and implement investment.

Third, offers a replicable empirical strategy for evaluating environmental metrics in macro-panel sustainability research. By holding the institutional and financial specification constant while varying only the ecological indicator, the analysis isolates the effect of metric choice on coefficient stability, theoretical

coherence, and substantive interpretation. This comparative strategy can be extended in future research to other regions and to alternative indicators of environmental pressure.

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